

Thermal Decomposition Studies on Oxo-Vanadium (IV) Complexes

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Several, recently synthesized oxo-vanadium(IV) complexes of pyridine— and quinoline carboxylic acid ligands have been studied by thermogravimetric and differential thermal analysis techniques. Besides elaborating on the temperature zone where a six coordinate oxo-vanadium(IV) species goes over to a five coordinated one, many otherwise untractable intermediates have been characterised.

As a result of development of newer techniques, studies on thermal dissociation of transition metal complexes have gained tremendous impetus and have attained a new height. Whereas most of the older reports concerned precipitates of interest from the stand-point of gravimetric estimation, the ones that are appearing during the last ten years, in particular, deal with coordination complexes of greater interest and these studies certainly have elucidated and characterised many of the transient states which are otherwise untractable. Besides thermogravimetry, many other techniques such as differential thermal analysis (DTA), gas evolution analysis (GEA), mass spectrometry, thermomagnetic studies as also high temperature reflectance spectroscopy (HTRS) are being increasingly applied in order to have better understanding.

Most of the reports in the recent chemical literature on thermal dissociation studies were concerned with Cobalt(II) and Cobalt(III), Mn(III), Cr(III), Cu(II), Ni(II), Rh(III) etc. to mention a few representative works¹⁻¹⁴. Currently studies on the synthesis, characterisation, spectral and magnetic studies of

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vanadium, in particular of Oxo-Vanadium(IV) complexes, have gained momentum¹⁵. We were surprised to see that the literature has a very limited number of detailed investigational report on Oxo-Vanadium(IV) complexes. Among these sporadic reports are one on aquo-oxo-bis-quinaldinato Vanadium(IV) by T.G.A.¹⁶, Oxo-monooxalato Vanadium(IV)¹⁷ and Oxo-pentaaquo-Vanadium(IV) perchlorate¹⁸ by T.G.A. and D.T.A. and one Oxo-dichloro bis-triphenylphosphine Vanadium(IV)¹⁹. Since our two schools at Burdwan and at Texas have been studying for several years now, Oxo-Vanadium(IV) complexes²⁰⁻²² on the one hand and the thermal decomposition of transition metal complexes on the other²³⁻²⁵, we found a common ground of mutual interest. This paper, arising out of that common interest, reports a study of thirteen Oxo-Vanadium(IV) complexes by the thermogravimetric analysis (T.G.A.) and the differential thermal analysis (D.T.A.) techniques.

The complexes chosen for the purpose are the Oxo-Vanadium(IV) complexes of pyridine and quinoline carboxylic acids. The following complexes have been studied by the above two techniques.

TABLE I

1. [VO(Py)(2-Q)] ₂	2. [VO(Py)(8-Q)] ₂
3. [VO(Anil)(2-Q)] ₂	4. [VO(Anil)(8-Q)] ₂
5. [VO(H ₂ O)(8-Q)] ₂ H ₂ O	6. [VO(H ₂ O)(Pic)] ₂
7. [VO(Py)(Pic)] ₂	8. [VO(Anil)(Pic)] ₂
9. [VO(H ₂ O)(Lut)] ₂ H ₂ O	10. [VO(Py)(H ₂ O)(Lut)] ₂
11. [VO(dipy)(Lut)] ₂ H ₂ O	12. [VO(acacH)(Lut)] ₂
13. [VO(glyH)(Lut)] ₂	

[PicH = Pyridine-2-Carboxylic acid; Py = Pyridine; Anil = aniline; 2-QH = Quinoline-2-Carboxylic acid; 8-QH = Quinoline-8-Carboxylic acid; Lut H₂ = Pyridine, 2,6-dicarboxylic acid; glyH = glycine; acacH = acetylacetonc.]

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The synthesis, characterisation, spectral and magnetic properties of these complexes have already been reported²⁰⁻²². Oxo-Vanadium(IV) complexes have in many cases been found in 5-coordinated as well as 6-coordinated species, the 5-coordinated ones going over to the 6-coordinated form under the influence of a nitrogen or an oxygen donor. Common examples of these types are $[\text{VO}(\text{X})(\text{acac})_2]$ and $[\text{VO}(\text{X})(2\text{-Q})_2]$, $[\text{VO}(\text{X})(8\text{-Q})_2]$, $[\text{VO}(\text{X})(\text{Pic})_2]$ to name a few where X is a donor such as pyridine, aniline, dimethylformamide, tetrahydrofuran etc. Thus thermal dissociation studies evidently would exhibit the range of stability of these two differently coordinated species besides revealing any other transient state, when the five coordinated species undergo further pyrolysis. Our choice of quinoline-2-carboxylic acid as also quinoline-8-carboxylic acid was expected to shed further light on the comparative stability of a five membered ring system against that of a six membered one.

The systems $[\text{VO}(\text{Py})(2\text{-Q})_2]$, $[\text{VO}(\text{Py})(8\text{-Q})_2]$ and $[\text{VO}(\text{H}_2\text{O})(8\text{-Q})_2]$:

Sharp decomposition begins for $[\text{VO}(\text{Py})(2\text{-Q})_2]$ at 125-130° and is over at 170°. The loss at this stage corresponds to a complete removal of the pyridine molecule forming $[\text{VO}(2\text{-Q})_2]$. This Oxo-bis-quinoline-2-Carboxylato Vanadium(IV) then remains stable upto 350° whereafter it suffers rapid decomposition and finally giving a steady TGA curve at 450°, at which stage the complex is totally decomposed to V_2O_5 . In keeping with the above TGA studies the DTA runs for this complex provides a sharp endothermic peak at 140°-142° and

FIG. 1

a second one at 370°. On comparing this system with the quinoline-8-carboxylate complex, it is observed that the first stage of decomposition corresponding to the loss of the pyridine addendum is completed over the range 135°-180°, followed by a steady stable state of $[\text{VO}(8\text{-Q})_2]$ upto 390°. The 5-coordinated

FIG. 2

species then starts decomposing over the range 390° – 550° , going over finally to the V_2O_5 stage. The first strong endothermic peak appears at 140° – 142° and the second, sharp peak at 400° . (Figs. 1 and 2).

TABLE II

Complex	Initial wt.	Aniline Pyridine loss		Total loss upto V_2O_5 stage	
		Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found
$[VO(Py)(2-Q)_2]$	57.5 mg.	9.27 mg.	9.0 mg.	46.82 mg.	47 mg.
$[VO(Py)(8-Q)_2]$	59.6 "	9.6 "	8.2 "	48.5 "	46 "
$[VO(Anil)(2-Q)_2]$	50.1 "	10.0 "	9.25 "	41.0 "	42.0 "
$[VO(Anil)(8-Q)_2]$	42.3 "	7.8 "	13.0 "	33.4 "	35.0 "

A comparison of the TGA and DTA curves for both these closely related Oxo-Vanadium(IV) complexes makes it realisable that whereas both the reactions

are initiated and completed over almost the same temperature region, the reactions leading to the decomposition to V_2O_5

are distinctly different. The quinoline-8-carboxylate complex shows a somewhat greater thermal stability than the corresponding quinoline-2-carboxylate complex.

The light yellow-brown $[\text{VO}(\text{H}_2\text{O})(8\text{-Q})_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ has also been investigated by the TGA and DTA techniques. The TGA curve initially shows a slow decomposition losing one H_2O but the second (coordinated) water is not totally lost before the setting in of the decomposition of the $[\text{VO}(8\text{-Q})_2]$. This probably suggests a stronger binding of the coordinated water compared to pyridine and aniline.

The systems $[\text{VO}(\text{Anil})(2\text{-Q})_2]$ and $[\text{VO}(\text{Anil})(8\text{-Q})_2]$:

First sign of decomposition is observed at $105^\circ - 110^\circ$ and is over by 150° , by which time of TGA curve shows correspondence to $[\text{VO}(2\text{-Q})_2]$. This latter complex, as in the above pyridine complex, then stays stable upto 330° and decomposes over the $330^\circ - 410^\circ$ region to go over to V_2O_5 . The DTA curve for the same compound reveals two comparable endothermic peaks at 130° and the other at $360^\circ - 370^\circ$.

The complex $[\text{VO}(\text{Anil})(8\text{-Q})_2]$ appears to hold the aniline rather strongly and shows the loss of aniline being complete at 250° . The loss at this stage is higher than what would have happened for aniline alone, indicating some slight decomposition of the $[\text{VO}(8\text{-Q})_2]$ species taking place simultaneously. The complex ultimately goes over to the V_2O_5 stage at 400° . The DTA curve of this particular complex is less prominent. (Figs. 1 and 2).

The systems $[\text{VO}(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{Pic})_2]$, $[\text{VO}(\text{Py})(\text{Pic})_2]$, and $[\text{VO}(\text{Anil})(\text{Pic})_2]$:

The aquo complex loses the water molecule within the range $200^\circ - 250^\circ$, showing that it is present in the complex inner sphere. The $[\text{VO}(\text{Pic})_2]$ complex thereafter, shows a stable region upto 340° and then gives a sharp big fall in the

FIG. 3

TGA curve upto 470° . The TGA curve at this state provides a composition V:Picolinic acid as 2:1 (Loss calculated upto $[\text{VO}_2(\text{Pic})(\text{OH})(\text{VO}_2)] = 31.2 \text{ mg}$; Found - 35 mg.). This transient stage then suffers a final decomposition and

FIG. 4

goes over to the V_2O_5 state at 610° . The DTA curve covering a temperature range upto 450° , shows the first two expected endothermic peaks at 230° and at 360° . (Figs. 3 and 4).

TABLE III

Complex	Initial wt. mg.	H ₂ O:Pyridine Aniline loss (mg.)		Loss upto V_2O_5 stage (mg.)	
		Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found
[VO(H ₂ O)(Pic) ₃]	58.2	3.2	3.5	42.3	43.0
[VO(Py)(Pic) ₃]	72.7	14.7	—	55.7	54.0
[VO(Anil)(Pic) ₃]	51.5	11.9	12.0	39.9	38.5

The pyridine complex does not lose the entire pyridine cleanly, seems to retain two thirds, which is lost along with the above second stage decomposition leading to a transient state of 2:1 metal : ligand complex (Loss calculated upto $[VO_2(Pic)(OH)(VO_2)] = 44.1$ mg, found 43 mg.). The DTA curve supports the results of the TGA studies. The aniline complex, however, loses aniline cleanly, provides evidence for $[VO(Pic)_2]$, which then goes over to the transient state and finally to the V_2O_5 state. (Figs. 3 and 4).

These complexes show that $[VO(Pic)_2]$ has almost the comparable thermal stability range as that of $[VO(2-Q)_2]$. However, in one respect, the two series differ. Whereas the Quinoline-2-carboxylate decomposes directly to V_2O_5 , that of Pyridine-2-carboxylate passes through a transient state, where one Pyridine-

2-carboxylic acid apparently bridges two Oxo-Vanadium entities. The temperature at which this stage occurs is favourable for the oxidation of Vanadium(IV)

to Vanadium(V). A tentative structure with a picolinic acid and OH bridge giving quinquevalence to Vanadium, such as the one given below, is proposed.

The systems $[VO(H_2O)_2(Lut)]H_2O$ and $[VO(H_2O)(Py)(Lut)]$:

The blue diaquo lutidinate Oxo-Vanadium(IV) monohydrate starts losing water at around 50° and the TGA curve shows the first plateau at about 130° . The loss at this state is lower than what would be expected for one molecule of water (Found 2.5 mg; Req'd=3.5 mg). This lower value may be attributed to a slow loss of water that the compound is known to have since its first obtaining in the blue form. This is followed by a short, stable zone upto about 160° and thereafter begins the second step dissociation, the complex going over to $[VO(H_2O)(Lut)]$. Once again we offer the same explanation for the "below theoretical" loss for the two molecules of water. The sample then starts the third step dissociation at 310° and exhibiting a minor break at 400° goes on to decompose to V_2O_5 at 520° . The DTA curve in essence supports these major dissociation steps, showing in all about five major endothermic peaks. (Figs. 3 and 4).

The complex $[VO(Py)(H_2O)(Lut)]$ is expected to give rise to at least three distinct dissociation steps. The TGA curve shows that the water dissociation and the pyridine loss steps are slightly overlapping. In this context, it is worthwhile to mention that around 120° in an oven prolonged heating changes the green $[VO(Py)(H_2O)(Lut)]$ to an intense navy blue $[VO(Py)(Lut)]$. Immediately after the first dissociation step is over, the complex starts the second dissociation step, which appears to get completed at 420° , giving $[VO(Lut)]$. This last species also is not quite stable at this temperature and decomposes immediately to V_2O_5 .

TABLE IV

Complex	Initial wt. mg.	Loss of Water mg.		Loss of Pyridine mg.		Loss upto V_2O_5	
		Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found
$[VO(H_2O)(Lut)]H_2O$	56.0	3.5	2.5	10.5	9.0	38.2	37.0
$[VO(Py)(H_2O)(Lut)]$	76.9	4.2	6.5	22.7	22.0	59.0	57.5

In agreement with all these behaviour by the TGA technique the DTA curves reveal three major peaks upto 400° . (Figs. 3 and 4).

The systems $[VO(Lut)(dipy)]H_2O$, $[VO(Lut)(acacH)]$ and $[VO(Lut)(glyH)]$:

The complex $[VO(Lut)(dipy)]H_2O$, as expected, shows in its TGA curve the regions of loss of water of hydration, then a plateau upto 270° , upto which region $[VO(Lut)(dipy)]$ is thermally stable. After this range, there is a sharp fall in the TGA curve, giving a stability region of 300° to 350° . This horizontal region corresponds to the composition $[VO(Lut) \frac{1}{2}(dipy)]$. This transient state then goes on to decompose to V_2O_5 . The stability zones of $[VO(Lut) \frac{1}{2}(dipy)]$ and $[VO(Lut)]$ are not well enough separated. The DTA curve for this complex is rather poor and the transition are less defined.

FIG. 5

The acetylacetonato complex $[VO(Lut)(acacH)]$ also shows like the dipyridyl complex a plateau, which stands for $[VO(Lut) \frac{1}{2}(acacH)]$. This is stable within the region 230° — 280° , and then proceeds to decompose, rather readily, going ultimately to the V_2O_5 stage. The TGA curve of the glycinato complex has also been studied and the dissociation steps appear to be over-lapping. (Fig. 5).

TABLE V

Complex	Initial wt. mg	Loss of water mg.		Loss of dipy acacH*	
		Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found
$[VO(Lut)(dipy)]H_2O$	47.2	2.1	2.5	11.21	10.5
$[VO(Lut)(acacH)]$	51.8	—	—	7.8	8.1

* Loss corresponding to $[VO(Lut) \frac{1}{2}(dipy)](acacH)$

The stage $[\text{VO}(\text{Lut})\frac{1}{2}(\text{dipy})]$ and $[\text{VO}(\text{Lut})\frac{1}{2}(\text{acacH})]$ are fairly distinct on the TGA curves. Apparently the complexes pass through a dipyriddy or acetylacetonone bridged structure of the following types.

These types of bridge structures are not unreasonable, in particular when two octahedra share an edge in common, the dipyriddy or the acetylacetonone need to bridge two points, which in essence, are cis-positions. As a support to such bridged intermediates, we might refer to a dipyriddy bridge structure in a titanium³⁴ complex and also to an intermediate in the thermal decomposition of tris-dipyriddy complexes of titanium(III)³⁵.

EXPERIMENTAL

The coordination complexes Oxo-Vanadium(IV) studied in this paper, have been recently described in a series of articles³⁰⁻³³. The purity of the complexes was checked by analysis and magnetic measurements prior to the thermal dissociation studies.

The TGA pyrolysis conditions were (a) air, static atmosphere; (b) 5°-6° per minute heating rate. For the DTA pyrolysis technique the conditions were as follows: (a) helium atmosphere, static condition; (b) 10°-11° per minute heating rate and (c) sample size of 30-50 mg.

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